

So everything is biased... now what?!¹

Introducing the Bias-Aware Framework for Dataset Creation

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Introduction

The digital humanities face an increasingly critical challenge. As computational methods become more deeply integrated with humanities research, the question of bias takes on new urgency - not just as a theoretical concern, but as a practical challenge that shapes every aspect of research. This urgency stems from the recognition that unexamined biases in institutions, (training) data, metadata, and computational methods risk amplifying historical exclusions and further marginalising already underrepresented narratives. Furthermore, these diverse forms of bias do not simply exist in parallel, but they compound and amplify each other throughout the research lifecycle. Yet, despite growing awareness of (harmful) bias in the digital humanities, the complexity and apparent ubiquity of bias has caused “bias paralysis” among many researchers and institutions: after all, everything is biased, so what can we do?

Moving away from the notion that biases should be fully removed from research – an impossible and unwanted task – the *Combatting Bias* (CB) project² proposes instead to treat “bias” as a productive category of analysis for digital humanities research through the development of a “Bias-Aware Framework”. It consists of three components: (1) a *Bias Thesaurus*, which establishes a shared vocabulary of ‘bias’ across disciplines to address its conceptual instability; (2) a *Data Lifecycle Model* showing where biases enter the research process; and (3) *Guidelines* for documenting, describing, and mitigating bias. We approach bias not simply as an error, but as a revealing analytical lens that shapes knowledge production. By explicitly describing these conditions of production, researchers can improve transparency, improve dataset documentation, and enable more informed reuse of their data. The Bias-Aware Framework will be discussed, tested, and improved upon during the workshop at DH Benelux 2025.

Scientific Scope and Aims

The workshop is designed to:

- **Deconstruct Bias** through the Bias Vocabulary.

¹ We are grateful to the anonymous reviewers of DH Benelux 2025 for their feedback on our abstract.

² Combatting Bias is a collaborative initiative based at the Huygens Institute and International Institute of Social History in Amsterdam, Netherlands. The authors are primary investigators on the project, working to establish frameworks for identifying and navigating bias in (historical) datasets. More information on the project, its partners and advisors can be found on the website: <https://combattingbias.huygens.knaw.nl/>

- **Test Practical Guidelines** created to identify, articulate and reduce harmful bias in datasets.
- **Encourage Ethical Intervention** for mitigating bias through the data life cycle, through transparent documentation and collection of new data.
- **Promote Bias Analysis and Mitigation** as crucial inclusion to the (digital humanities') research agenda.

Workshop Specifications

- **Length:** Half-day (3 hours)
- **Number of participants:** Maximum 20
- **Format:** Hybrid (in-person and virtual participation)

Workshop Leaders

This workshop will be led by researchers from the *Combatting Bias* project, with expertise in colonial histories, data ethics, and digital (historical) infrastructures:

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Workshop Participants

Target Participants

- Dataset creators and users
- Digital humanities researchers
- Cultural heritage professionals

Technical Requirements

- Participants should bring laptops
- No technical expertise required
- Option to work with own dataset. Example datasets will also be provided

Background

Digital humanities researchers face a unique challenge: they must grapple with **multiple forms of bias that intersect across different disciplines and stages of research**. A single digital humanities project might simultaneously confront archival biases in source selection (Trouillot, 1995), historical power structures in interpretation (van Rossum, 2019), representational biases in digitisation (Kizhner et al., 2021), and algorithmic biases in computational analysis (Buolamwini & Gebru, 2018; Mehrabi et al., 2021; Søgaard et al., 2014; Suresh & Guttag, 2021). These biases encountered do not remain isolated, as historical biases in archival selection get encoded into metadata structures, which then inform algorithmic design, creating feedback loops that can dramatically magnify originally subtle imbalances. This cascading effect of bias creates a distinctive challenge that requires a systematic approach rather than isolated interventions. This compounding effect means that seemingly minor biases at early stages can result in significantly skewed outcomes during analysis, interpretation, and beyond.

While there are several valuable contributions towards practical mitigation of bias, including templates for transparent documentation and alternatives to harmful terminology (Alkemade et al., 2023; Bender & Friedman, 2018; Chilcott, 2022; Luthra & Eskevich, 2024; Masschelein et al., 2023; Modest & Lelijveld, 2018; Scheuerman et al., 2020), they typically address specific manifestations of bias - there is therefore a lack of a coherent framework for understanding and reducing bias in its many intersecting forms.

One critical challenge is the lack of a consistent definition for bias across fields, from natural language processing to cultural heritage (Blodgett et al., 2020; McCullagh, 2000), which means there is no common vocabulary when one wishes to address the issue. Furthermore, digital humanists must perform a particularly intricate balancing act, honoring both historical authenticity and contemporary social justice while simultaneously addressing technical concerns of algorithmic fairness. Digital humanities researchers need tools that can help them address the full spectrum of biases they encounter: from historical biases to technical biases to representation biases. Moreover, they need to understand how these different forms of bias interact and transform across the stages of their work.

We propose to address these challenges by reconceptualising bias as a productive tool of analysis. Drawing inspiration from Joan Scott's (2010) concept of gender as an analytical category and Sherman et al.'s (2024) treatment of algorithmic absences, we argue that 'bias', like Foucault's concept of power, is relational and dynamic, actively shaping and being shaped by social, cultural, and historical contexts (Foucault & Hurley, 2008).³ This perspective shifts our focus from attempting to *solve* bias –an impossible task– to using bias as a critical tool for reflection and analysis. With this reconceptualisation at the foundation, we are developing a "Bias Aware Framework" which has the the three corresponding components:

- A **Bias Thesaurus**: A comprehensive list of the concepts connected to bias (such as representation, offensive language, FAIR, CARE, silences, etc.) that creates a shared vocabulary for discussing bias across disciplines (see Figure 1). Please note, at the moment the Thesaurus is only a Vocabulary.
- A **Bias-Aware Data Lifecycle Model**: Showing where and how bias manifests at different research stages, allowing for targeted interventions at critical points (see Figure 2).
- **Guidelines and Toolkit**: Reflective questions at each stage of the dataset lifecycle, illustrative examples, and "good-better-best" recommendations for specific bias analysis, description, and mitigation.

³ Looking at its evolution across linguistic and cultural spheres, we find that different languages reveal how bias is understood through varied sensory and conceptual metaphors: visual (French "biais"/slant, Chinese "偏見"/slanted-view), social-political (Sanskrit "पक्षपात"/partisanship, taking sides), temporal-cognitive (Hindi "पूर्वाग्रह"/prior-grasping), and positional (Arabic "تحيز"/taking-a-position, aligning-oneself). Each etymology emphasises different aspects of how bias operates in human understanding: through sight, social alignment, time, and positioning.

Figure 1: Bias as heuristic for distinct yet interrelated issues.

Figure 2: The Bias-Aware Lifecycle Model. The expressions of bias associated with each stage are contextualised in the Thesaurus and Guidelines.

Guidelines for Bias Analysis and Mitigation

The Guidelines for identifying, articulating and reducing bias exist on two levels:

1. **Lifecycle Guidelines**, which are process-oriented and propose stage-by-stage interventions.
2. **Bias Thesaurus Good-Better-Best⁴ Guidelines**, which specific expressions of bias receive recommended interventions across the whole research data lifecycle.

The Guidelines include:

⁴ The good-better-best-framework has been humbly taken over from Chilcott (2022).

- Reflective questions for analysis
- Relevant literature and existing approaches (including relevant documentation templates)
- Good-better-best practices for mitigation
- Examples from digital humanities projects

These guidelines were made in collaboration with CB's project partners - Slave Voyages, GLOBALISE, Exploring Slave Trade in Asia, and Historische Databases of Suriname and Curaçao - all of which are developing digital infrastructures and datasets concerning sensitive themes of colonialism and slavery.

Examples of Bias Description and Mitigation in Practice

During the workshop, participants will explore real-world examples of bias and learn how to apply the Bias-Aware Framework to mitigate these issues. Below, Figure 3 and Figure 4, are two examples of the Good-Better-Best Guidelines for key expressions of bias.

Harmful Languages^a

Definition: Language that causes uncomfot, pain, feelings of unsafety to an individual or group of people.

Reflective questions

- What does your research understand by 'offensive terminology'? What is the source of this understanding?
- What processes exist in your project for identifying potentially offensive terms?
- Is it relevant for your project to document offensive terminology?
- Along what lines is terminology offensive (e.g. ethnonreligious, gender and sexuality, race, (dis)ability)?^b

Example dataset: Thesaurus Creation in the GLOBALISE project^c

Good practice	Better practice	Best practice
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present offensive terms taken directly from the archive in quotation marks. • Do not substitute offensive terms with a modern equivalent. • Include a content warning explaining usage of offensive terms • Reference community-approved guidelines (such as Words Matter, DE-BIAS, Cultural Heritage Terminology Network). • Integrate this information into the data-envelope^d and documentation^e accompanying the dataset. 	<p><i>In addition to 'good practices':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create research guides with relevant search terms and context about offensive language in historical records. • Acknowledge the evolving nature of terminology guidelines. • Explain that words were or were not maintained from (primary) sources and/or other datasets, and explaining why this decision was made. 	<p><i>In addition to 'better practices':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implement participatory methods for tagging and description. • During annotation, use alt- and pre-labels to curate how your dataset will be viewed and read. • Consider replacing offensive language in primary user-facing description. • Integrate a discussion of problematic language into the project plan and workflow early-on in the project. • Consult communities and experts on terminology. • Create standardized institutional language that can be reused. See resources below. • Select tools that enable separate processing of sensitive terms (e.g. DE-BIAS). • Document all decisions in documentation and data-envelopes. • Maintain versioned documentation with clear update plans.

Resources

- **Chilcott, Alicia.** "Towards Protocols for Describing Racially Offensive Language in UK Public Archives." In Archives in a Changing Climate - Part I & Part II, edited by Viviane Frings-Hessami and Fiorella Foscarini, 151–68. Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature Switzerland, 2022. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-19289-0_10.
- **DE-BIAS:**
 - Vocabulary: <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/the-de-bias-vocabulary>
 - Identification tool: <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/the-de-bias-tool>
- **Words Matter:** <https://www.materialculture.nl/en/publications/words-matter>
- **Inclusive Terminology Glossary:** <https://culturalheritageterminology.co.uk/>
- **Indigenous Peoples Terminology:** <https://www.ictinc.ca/blog/indigenous-peoples-terminology-guidelines-for-usage>
- **DEI Controlled Vocabls List:** https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/19solOX6tQTYvIF4lr_JNz2WlcsA76CcK3bxvYZ8cHzg/edit?gid=0#gid=0
- **Gender, Sex and Sexual Orientation:** <https://gsso.research.cchmc.org/#/> (linked data)
- **Homosaurus:** <https://homosaurus.org/> (linked data)

^a Chilcott's (2019) framework addresses racially offensive language specifically - this example therefore incorporates her proposed protocols as well.

^b For more, see the 'wheel of bias' developed by the DE-BIAS project, in Beirigo & Groot (2024).

^c This dataset which is currently under construction defines and creates a taxonomy of concepts that feature in the archives of the Dutch East India Company. As many of these concepts are referred to by labels that are problematic and derogatory, conceptualizing a method of addressing problematic language in this dataset is an important component of dataset creation.

^d Developed by Luthra & Eskevich (2024), data-envelopes are machine-readable forms of dataset documentation (also known as datasheets in machine learning), tackling the specific needs and challenges of cultural heritage datasets.

^e Documentation refers to the descriptive account of dataset creation which accompanies the publication of a dataset. Documentation provides the contextualizing information for a dataset from a disciplinary point of view, that a data-envelope does not, or only briefly provides.

Figure 3: Guidelines for dealing with Harmful Language in research.

Silences^a

Definition: “a gap in the (historical) record resulting from the unintentional or purposeful absence or distortion of documentation.” This goes for both the documentation as well as processes and institutional policies.^a

Reflective questions

- What gaps are you trying to fill in your research? Time period, geography, actors, concepts?
- What groups, voices, or perspectives are missing from your sources?
- How do these silences impact potential research questions and findings?
- What alternative sources might help address these gaps?
- How can silences be made visible to users?

Example dataset: Globalise Namebooks^b

Good practice	Better practice	Best practice
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Discuss silences of the archive and/or sources with your research team.• Recognize archival silences in source utilized and notify users about them in your documentation and contextualisation, and/or visualisations.	<p><i>In addition to 'good practices':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Document acknowledgement and discussion of silences, gaps and absences in your dataset.• Speak to others (communities and/or academics) to understand the impact and extent of the silences.• Scout for and incorporate alternative sources to imbalances of the source.	<p><i>In addition to 'better practices':</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Document silences, gaps and absences in your research - during setup, collection, and processing stages. It is helpful to reflect on your positionality, through description of policies and practices that led to your research (outcomes).• Employ tools that allow you to tackle and overcome past silences. For example, descriptions of archival records which were often the gateways for research have very often been biased and only bear mention of persons that were of relevance to the archival creator. Present technologies like HTR (Handwritten Text Recognition) help you bypass document descriptions and recover all person mentions in a certain archive.• Actively make - tackling silences, exploring alternative source material, and involving alternate perspectives on sources- part of your research objective and plan and budget for these activities.• Document all decisions in documentation and data-envelopes.• Maintain versioned documentation with clear update plans.

Resources

- **Trouillot, Michel-Rolph** (1995). *Silencing the Past: Power and the Production of History*. Beacon Press.
- **Handwritten Text Recognition (HTR)**, such as **Transkribus**: <https://www.transkribus.org/>

^a Society of American Archivists (n.d.). Dictionary of Archives Terminology. <https://dictionary.archivists.org/entry/archival-silence.html>.

^b This dataset features a skewed gender representation where only a small minority of women is featured in the sources. The dataset (and its corresponding documentation and data-envelope) of the Namebooks of the Dutch East India Company (1730-1794) can be found here: <https://hdl.handle.net/10622/DITM0Z>

Figure 4: Guidelines for dealing with Silences in research.

During the workshop, feedback on the guidelines are encouraged – this discussion will help refine the guidelines, helping us shape them to be widely applicable for datasets across the social sciences and humanities field.

About Combatting Bias

Combatting Bias is a one-year project funded by the NWO via the Thematic Digital Competence Centre Social Sciences & Humanities (TDCC-SSH), which focuses on the ethical creation of datasets for the social sciences and humanities. It particularly focuses on the dataset, because creators, users, and digital infrastructures intersect at this point, making it a good unit of analysis. Our work is enriched by partnerships with leading digitisation initiatives and advisors from different geographies and disciplines such as museum studies, critical archival studies, ethnomusicology, history, computer science, and economics.

Workshop Program

We envision the workshop to run a half-day programme (preferably in the afternoon), for 3 hours. The workshop will be divided into three parts (excluding breaks):

Session	Time
Introduction	15 minutes
Activity 1: Mindmapping Bias	40 minutes
Discussion	25 minutes
Break	15 minutes
Introducing the Framework	20 minutes
Activity 2: Best Practices for Bias Mitigation	40 minutes
Discussion	20 minutes
Closing Remarks	5 minutes

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